

Catalogue of Widgets and Devices to support the Awareness Design of New-Generation Collaborative Environments (NGCE)

Widget (or controller)	Senses / Categories (*)						Purpose
W1.1 Participant list	✓						To show the list of participants in the activity, their roles and abilities.
W1.2 Personal profile	✓						To show information related to a participant.
W1.3 Group/Personal state	✓						To show the working states of the participants or group (e.g., reading, modelling, writing, disconnected).
W1.4 Group structure/hierarchy	✓						To show the structure and hierarchy of the group of users collaborating.
W1.5 Input/Working area highlighting	✓						Colouring of data, artifacts or working areas with the user's assigned colour.
W1.6 Last activities / Event list	✓						Lists the actions or events carried out in the activity and tasks execution.
W1.7 Participation-meter	✓						Represents the degree of participation of the users.
W1.8 Activity progress view	✓						To show a structured view of the progress of the activity the users are carrying out.
W1.9 Artifact-based activity view	✓						To show a view of the activity through the artefacts managed in the tasks.
W1.10 Task progress bar	✓						Represents the progress of the ongoing activity and its tasks.
W1.11 Collaborative editor / Shared text pane	✓						Shared text and feedback/feedthrough effects of a collaborative editing area.
W1.12 Artefact/Tool colouring	✓						To show artefacts/tools with colouring according to authors/owners.
W1.13 Visual cue	✓						Represents graphical and visual cues to highlight events or properties.
W1.14 Collaborative map	✓						Represents a geographic shared map with collaborative behaviour.
W1.15 Tele-pointer	✓						Represents the exact location where users are interacting on a shared surface or working area.
W1.16 Group scrollbar	✓						Scrollbar that contains multiple bars, each corresponding to a user of the group to scroll through the working area.
W1.17 Radar view	✓						To show a miniature overview of the working surface or activity space, in 2D or 3D.
W1.18 Fish-eye view	✓						To view the working surface or activity space as a fish-eye: nearby elements larger, distant ones smaller.
W1.19 Heat map	✓						Represents the activity on a heat map with colouring expressing user working intensity.
W1.20 User position and movement orientation	✓						Represents the users' physical position in a natural space and the direction they are facing.
W1.21 Action sphere	✓						To show the sphere of influence for the users' action, according to the task being developed.
W1.22 Field of view	✓						To show which region a user is viewing.
W1.23 Rays	✓						Visual extensions from a source, such as a user's glasses or controller.
W1.24 Tele-portal	✓						To view another user's complete view.
W1.25 Coordination semaphores	✓						Visual component to manage low-level coordination tasks to decision-making or assignments.
W1.26 Voting results	✓						To show the results of a voting process.
W1.27 Video playback	✓						Reproduction of video (e.g., in videoconferencing –see Audio playback–).
W1.28 Meeting agenda	✓						To show a shared agenda.
W1.29 Shared digital clock	✓						A clock shared by all group members.
W1.30 Body/Physiological information panel	✓						Visual representation of users' physiological parameters.
W1.31 Environmental information panel	✓		✓				Representation of climate parameters, atmospheric phenomena, or other environmental data.
W1.32 User emotional representation	✓						To display a representation of a user's emotional state or mood.
W1.33 Avatar	✓						Static or dynamic avatar representation of the user in full-body, half-body, or head and hands.
W1.34 Reaction / Reaction panel	✓		✓				To show feedback about gestures or emotional responses.
W1.35 Hands	✓						Visual representation of other users' hands to facilitate non-verbal communication.
W1.36 Group version of single-user widget	✓						Single-user widget adapted for shared or collaborative behaviour.
W2.1 Touch Input controller		✓					Controller for managing input from touch devices.
W2.2 Touch Output controller		✓					Controller for managing output to touch devices.
W2.3 Sight-Touch controller	✓	✓					Controller for managing both input and output from touch devices.
W3.1 Audio playback					✓		Reproduction of audio (e.g., for calls or videoconferencing –see Video playback–)
W3.2 Audio cues					✓		Playback of audio cues or alarms.
W3.3 Speech recognition					✓		Controller for recognizing speech.
W3.4 Voice synthesizer					✓		Controller to synthesize voice and speech.
W3.5 Proximity sonar					✓		Controller to manage proximity detection using an audio sonar.
W3.6 Sound and music generator					✓		Controller to generate and play sound and music.
W3.7 Sound and music processor					✓		Controller to process and analyse sound and music sources.
W4.1 Smell controller						✓	Controller to analyse and reproduce smells.
W5.1 Emotion recognizer						✓	Controller to capture and compute facial or bodily expressions of users.
W5.2 Facial and corporal expression generator						✓	To build and show facial or bodily expressions of users.
W5.3 Physiological controller						✓	Controller to manage physiological parameters.
W6.1 Positioning controller						✓	Controller to manage the user's positioning system.
W6.2 Environment controller						✓	Controller for interacting with the environment.

(*) : Sight. : Touch. : Hearing : Smell. : Physiological parameters. : Environment.

Device	Modality	Senses / Categories						Function
D1.1 Screen	O	✓						Displays information visually, whether from a PC, smart phone, XR headset, or smart glasses.
D1.2 Camera	I	✓						Captures the user's face or body.
D1.3 Enhanced camera	I	✓						Captures thermal, night-vision, or LIDAR-based imagery.
D2.1 Mouse	I		✓					Pointer device for direct interaction.
D2.2 Keyboard	I		✓					Text and command input device.
D2.3 Haptic glove	I/O		✓					Glove for capturing finger/hand motion or providing haptic feedback.
D2.4 Vibrating bracelet	O		✓					Wearable device that provides vibration-based notifications or cues.
D2.5 Fingerprint sensor	I		✓					Fingerprint recognition and identification.
D2.6 XR headset controller	I/O		✓					Mixed Reality hand-held controller.
D2.7 Game controller	I/O		✓					Hand-held device used for controlling gameplay or simulations.
D2.8 Touchscreen	I/O	✓	✓					Display that responds to finger touch.
D2.9 Interactive table	I/O	✓	✓					Horizontal surface enabling multi-user touch-based interaction.
D2.10 Interactive whiteboard	I/O	✓	✓					Large display that supports collaborative, touch-based interaction.
D2.11 Smartwatch	I/O	✓	✓					Wearable device for tracking user activity, notifications and computing.
D3.1 Speakers	O					✓		External audio output device.
D3.2 Earphones	O					✓		Personal audio output device, usually in-ear.
D3.3 Microphone	I					✓		Device for capturing voice or ambient sound.
D3.4 XR headset	I/O	✓	✓	✓				Wearable device integrating visual, audio and touch output for XR experiences.
D3.5 Smart glasses	I/O	✓		✓				Smart glasses device with visual and hearing capabilities.
D4.1 Electronic nose (scent sensor)	I					✓		Device that detects and interprets scents or airborne chemicals.
D4.2 Smell generator	O					✓		Device that synthesizes and emits artificial scents.
D5.1 Eye tracker	I						✓	Tracks gaze direction and eye movements.
D5.2 Activity tracker (bracelet)	I	✓					✓	Monitors physical activity and body motion.
D5.3 Heart ECG	I						✓	Records the electrical activity of the heart.
D5.4 Brain EEG	I						✓	Measures brainwave activity.
D5.5 Heart rate bracelet	I	✓					✓	Detects and displays the user's heart rate.
D5.6 Thermometer / Thermal bracelet	I	✓					✓	Measures and reports body temperature.
D5.7 Electrical stimulation device	O						✓	Sends electrical pulses to stimulate nerves.
D6.1 Digital bodysuit	I/O		✓				✓	Full-body suit for motion capture, haptic feedback and biofeedback.
D6.2 GPS	I						✓	Detects the user's global location.
D6.3 IPS	I						✓	Detects the user's indoor position.
D6.4 Gyroscope	I						✓	Measures orientation and angular velocity.
D6.5 Accelerometer	I						✓	Detects linear acceleration and movement.
D6.6 Speedometer	I						✓	Measures speed of motion or travel.
D6.7 RFID receiver	I						✓	Detects nearby RFID-tagged objects.
D6.8 RFID activator	O						✓	Sends signals to activate RFID tags.
D6.9 Omni-directional treadmill	I						✓	Allows walking and movement in any direction while remaining in place.

References

Bravo, C., Molina, A.I., Ortega-Cordovilla, M. (2025) Patterns and widgets for collaboration awareness in next-generation groupware. 7th World Symposium on Software Engineering (WSSE 2025), October 24-26, 2025, Okayama, Japan. ACM, New York, NY, USA

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- W1.31 Environmental information panel
- W1.34 Reaction / Reaction panel

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- W5.1 Emotion recognizer
- W5.2 Facial and corporal expression generator
- W5.3 Physiological controller

- W6.1 Positioning controller
- W6.2 Environment controller

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- D2.6 XR headset controller
- D2.7 Game controller
- D2.8 Touchscreen
- D2.9 Interactive table
- D2.10 Interactive whiteboard
- D2.11 Smartwatch
- D3.1 Speakers
- D3.2 Earphones
- D3.3 Microphone
- D3.4 XR headset
- D3.5 Smart glasses
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